

LIMITATIONS OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND RISK MANAGEMENT PERFORMANCE IN AIR TRANSPORT DUE TO TECHNOLOGY AND THE DYNAMICS AND UNPREDICTABILITY OF THE GLOBAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

Purpose – *The paper highlights specific challenges in relation to inter-organizational communication and cooperation and analyzes safety management limitations due to lack of predictability which can lead to cascading events.*

Methodology/approach – *The research method combines a thorough literature review, analysis of the means of control used in safety management worldwide for keeping risk at an acceptable level and evaluation of monitoring methods which must ensure functionality.*

Findings – *The study identifies what kind of decisions affect the probability of an event to develop cascading effects and what are the influencing factors for decision failure.*

Research limitations/implications – *The paper researches the drawbacks of management processes and strategies in achieving operational performance while dealing with technological complexity and the unpredictability of the global environment due to research and development dynamics, economic instability, or even pandemics.*

Practical implications – *The outcome of different managerial decisions is identified and the connections between the initiator system and the dependent system when an intervention can prevent an event from having cascade effects are established.*

Originality/value – *After reviewing the limitations of safety performances and organizational management success, the authors propose that the framework for safety risk assessment must be outlined by a network-type combinatorial structure comprising elements of knowledge.*

Key words: *cascading effects, safety risk management, technological complexity.*

Introduction

In a global environment, dealing with the technological complexity of the system must be supported by effective risk management as a foundation for strategic decisions which must be made long before cascading events occur. Many aeronautical organizations provide safety performance indicators based on generic categories and specific programs because they are easier to measure and by doing this, it offers a false sense of comfort that risks are being managed. While these indicators are important in the context of organizational culture and leadership, they are very rarely used in the initiation phase of a safety event.

Safety risks associated with high-impact events that are less likely to occur represent the trigger for the analysis of specific management challenges related to the dynamics and lack of predictability of aviation environment. The authors study the interdependence of modern aviation systems and their implications on risk management. Although these interdependencies make the systems more efficient during normal operations, they contribute to cascading effects in times of crisis. The research method analysis primary and secondary data; thus, after reviewing different studies, surveys and reports, indicators related to safety performance are assessed and the limitations of management performance are outlined.

The drawbacks of poor managerial decisions in aviation regarding safety are outlined in the context of global instability, pandemics outbreak and the development of complex technologies that on one hand have had a decisive impact in reducing accident rates, but on the other hand, affected decision making due to additional information, influenced the attitude towards risk in a negative way and generated a series of errors that led to accidents.

Technological complexity in the aeronautical system - a network of knowledge

In aviation, technologies have reached high levels of complementarity that require multi-technological activities, an additional aspect to complexity due to the development and application in the operational environment (Fai & Von Tunzelmann, 2001). The pattern that technological complexity has provided over time reflects in the detail, intricacy and difficulty of the measures applied.

Technological complexity is seen as an explanatory dimension of technological success and development (Romer, 1990; Dalmazzo, 2002). Hidalgo and Hausmann (2009) state that the success of a system depends on the ability to manage complex technologies and economic activities, while Fleming and Sorenson (2001) offer an approach to technological complexity by conceptualizing technological advances as a research process for combining knowledge. Knowledge can be outlined by a network of combinations in which nodes represent individual pieces of cognition, and their combinations represent the links between them. Surely, an aircraft can be represented as a combined knowledge network, with directly and indirectly linked elements. As a measure of aircraft technological complexity, a combinatorial structure of the network type can be used, comprising elements of knowledge. Nevertheless, the difficulty of combining elements of knowledge can be determined by a precise structure in which technological elements are integrated, giving rise to innovation processes.

Progress in technical systems development and manufacturing processes leads to modes of complex failures and reliability issues in the product life cycle. In the spectrum of capital/industrial goods, the consequences of concessions can be directly related to safety issues affecting people - in the event of incidents or accidents. This represents major challenges for engineering reliability processes in the final product life cycle. Reliability methods/techniques need to be improved and adapted in order to ensure product reliability and production capacity (Bracke et al. 2017).

In order to identify safety issues and characterize initiating events, the connections, dependencies between different systems, past incidents with cascading effects must be studied and understood - their knowledge and understanding is the basis for development of appropriate response algorithms. A cascading event showing recent technological vulnerabilities is reflected in the two Boeing 737 MAX accidents from Indonesia (Lion Air Flight 610) and Etiopia (Ethiopian Airlines Flight 302) from 2018, respectively 2019, having one thing in common: they were not equipped with safety features that could have prevented accidents. The initiating event (a sensor calibration error) led to automatic actuation of the trimmer control located on the horizontal rudder. Due to the way MCAS (Maneuvering Characteristics Augmentation System) was conceived, there was unlimited number of flight control actuations which led to an unbalance of the aircraft (excessive trimming) which exceeded the crew's ability to control the depth control (cascading events), thus forcing the aircraft into uncontrolled dive.

The lacking elements of knowledge consist of an operational problem: the fact that Boeing did not provide any information to the pilots about the existence and operation of the system in the preparation phase - to make the transition on the 737 MAX aircraft, nor were they registered information in the Operating Manuals for 737 MAX or in the QHR (Quick Reference Book). Therefore, the crew could not identify the cause of the in-flight control problems of the aircraft, failing to reach a solution, thus failing to provide a network of knowledge.

In the context of events with (or with a high risk of producing) cascading effects as presented above, human activities and decision can play a significant role in unfolding events and cascading effects. The specifics of aircraft systems must be known in order to solve unforeseen situations regardless of the context and phase of the flight. Aeronautical systems undergo technological changes in a staged manner; the biggest problem is the impact of that technology on the operation of the whole system; and in this particular case, the new features and characteristics, restrictions and limitations of operation should have been taken into account. A new, modern technological system has an impact on the entire

system in which it is implemented; given the multitude of organizations involved in aeronautics this impact is a connected one.

Barrier strategies and management limitations in achieving operational performance

Safety control does not imply only barriers of a physical nature, such as protective equipments and systems; but also administrative processes and critical safety activities that are carried out by the organization's staff. The need to understand interaction between technical, organizational and operational elements that play a role in performing safety barrier functions is important in order to be successful in implementation of risk assessment process. Of course, the knowledge on defining performance requirements for organizational and operational elements and how to achieve their inclusion in the specific barrier strategy is also very important.

In general, management is important as an influencing factor for performance, but it is not a barrier element; it helps to ensure that routine and resources are adequate for setting and maintaining barriers. The limitations of management performance are given by the lack of predictability of the aviation safety environment. Lordache et al. (2018) show that predictability is narrowed not only during concept phase, but also in operational processes due to performance variability – which should not be counted as a negative aspect like performance deviation.

However, specific roles in management and the functions they may perform can represent barriers of organizational or operational nature. The contribution of the human factor is extremely important in barrier functions. The performance requirements are intended to verify that each individual barrier is effective; performance requirements must be clear and verifiable both organizationally and operationally (Lauridsen et al. 2016).

Significant concerns have risen in current challenging circumstances for the aviation industry due to Covid-19 global health emergency. In aviation, this infectious disease represents a high-impact event unlikely to occur; however, this initiating event (the pandemics) has led to unexpected safety related cascading effects. Safety occurrence has been reported lately, including real hazards such as tail strikes and exceeding the assigned altitude due to a lower take-off weight of the aircraft caused by a small load factor, or even the inability to maintain cabin pressure (Pallini, 2020). On top of this, pilots losing their skills and abilities after a long period in which they no longer practiced, require refresher training or even medical help to deal with fear or stress as responses to perceived safety threats. This has led to severe cascading effects and quickly became very difficult to manage by using pre-established response measures. The more vulnerable the system is due to the environment, the greater the risk of cascading effects.

In this case, technical barriers are not suitable, but organizational measures can be applied for achieving operational performance again. According to Kilskar et al. (2017), operational barrier elements represent information that provides assistance in carrying out a specific task. The spectrum in which they provide support is broad; so it can be a benefit in distinguishing different categories of safety critical procedures. Operational barrier elements can only be considered those that are critical to activating the barrier function after an event occurs and those that are important in order to prevent initiation of the unwanted event. These procedures are required in order to activate the barrier function. Also, performance requirements must be set to follow these organizational barriers. From an organizational point of view, the barrier elements are represented by the staff with well-defined roles or specific functions and skills; which helps to achieve the barrier role (Lauridsen et al. 2016). Withal, maintaining and ensuring barriers integrity across operational spectrum, including verification and evaluation of performance barriers is needed (Hauge et al., 2016) (see fig 1).

From the management standpoint, the response to such situations must be as effective as possible and built on recent and verifiable information - this information comes in support of decision making processes. Surely, in aviation, keeping risks to a minimum it's compulsory, thus the role of predictive analysis is imperative; but this is achieved by collecting large amounts of data to make predictions. In the real or perceived hazard cases related to ongoing pandemic, this was not possible or feasible. This situation highlights the importance of a safety knowledge network. It must be acknowledged that decision making is a collaborative effort that unites several groups with different visions of situations, decisions and actions (Bram et al., 2016). This creates the need for a common ground and shared

mental models for decision making. The possibility of achieving this, during an event involving cascading effects, increases with the understanding of how it works and the knowledge of equipment and tools available and understanding the characteristics of members/team/organization including their knowledge of skills, beliefs and efforts of others (Lönnermark and Lange, 2017).

Figure 1. The process of barrier management in operation (adapted after Kilskar et al., 2016)

An important aspect is to identify the effects of different decisions, in order to find key decision points; for example, opportunities to affect connections between the initiator system and the dependent system when an intervention can prevent a cascading event. The aim is not to fully analyze how decisions are made, as it can be very difficult to determine, but to find out what kind of decisions affect development during a cascading incident. How an incident is considered to be complex, stressful, or difficult to understand depends on both the experience of receiver and the ability to understand information received. From the point of view of the decision-maker and possible success, influencing factors can be considered the following: system capacity and ability, interface, stress, workload, motivation, complexity, training, experience, culture, social dynamics such as group effects, how to carry out processes and organizations structures.

Discussion and conclusions

Without sufficient investment in modern aviation technologies, catastrophes can occur, although the goal of research and development of new technologies was to represent a benefit. Understanding escalation processes requires knowledge of initiation elements and the dependencies between systems, physical phenomenon and key decision points in crisis situations. New strategies, structures and methodologies are needed to withstand and manage evolving challenges, including inter-institutional or inter-organizational cooperation in conducting operations and providing or receiving support regardless of the operational environment.

Mapping existing performance standards or a logical model that presents the relationships between barrier elements within a barrier function is important. In the situation of identifying organizational barrier elements, it is preferable to differentiate between the normal operational organization and the organization of the emergency response. The inter-organizational situation, the way it is managed, and the level at which decisions are taken and communicated, may differ depending on the country and regions; even if there is international standardization, the impact of regional/national culture is reflected in organizational management processes.

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